

Prediction of rain erosion damage progression using disdrometer rain data: The importance of liquid water content

Ásta Hannesdóttir, Ebba Dellwik, Charlotte Bay Hasager

DTU Wind and Energy Systems, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, Denmark

E-mail: astah@dtu

Abstract. Wind turbine blade erosion poses a significant challenge to the durability and performance of wind turbines. Modeling of rain erosion damage, considering atmospheric conditions, improves our understanding of the progression of leading-edge erosion on wind turbine blades. In this study, we investigate the impact of varying raindrop characteristics on rain erosion damage development. We analyse 2.5 years of data from a disdrometer, which measures the size and velocity of falling rain droplets, at Risø campus. Various post-processing methods of the disdrometer data are used for estimating representative droplet diameters and fall velocities for each rain event. We compare measured droplet fall velocities with theoretical terminal velocities, revealing a necessity for revising theoretical approaches to raindrop fall velocity for erosion damage modeling. The measured rain rates and representative fall velocities are used to calculate the liquid water content in the air. We introduce a bin-wise summation method for estimating the liquid water content, circumventing the need for representative droplet assumptions. As this method provides the most accurate input for the damage model, we benchmark the other post-processing methods against it and employ it to evaluate bias estimates of associated damage predictions. The largest bias (22%) in accumulated damage is found with an arithmetic mean droplet diameter approach and the smallest bias (-2%) with the median volume estimation method for damage model input. Furthermore, we demonstrate that, for a given rainfall volume, smaller droplets contribute to larger accumulated damage compared to larger droplets.

1. Introduction

The degradation of wind turbine blades due to leading-edge erosion is significantly impacted by the atmospheric conditions prevailing at specific sites [1, 2]. Atmospheric phenomena such as hail, lightning, UV radiation can damage coating on the blades, but in particular, precipitation and high concurrent wind speeds have been identified as key influences in this process [3]. In this study we focus on blade material damage caused by rain and concurrent wind speed only. The progression of rain erosion damage can be modeled with a fatigue-based damage model, with observed wind speed and rainfall characteristics as input data. Fatigue-based rain erosion models establish a relationship between the impact speed of the blade tip and the impingement of rain at the point of coating failure through a so-called Wöhler curve. Wöhler curves for blade materials are determined through a manual inspection process involving blade specimens that have been subjected to a rain-erosion tester [4].

This study examines how the characterization of rain eventst based on observational disdrometer rain data influences the modeled progression of rain erosion damage. We use data from a laser-optical disdrometer, which measures the size and velocity of raindrops passing through its emitted and received horizontal laser light plane, providing the joint distribution of droplet size and fall velocity. In the modeling of damage progression, estimating the liquid water content in the air is a critical step. Typically, the liquid water content of a rain event is computed for a droplet diameter that is representative of that event. Representative droplets commonly used for blade damage models include a mass-weighted mean [1, 5], the median volume diameter [6, 7, 5], and a theoretically estimated diameter based on rain rate [8, 9], used when only rain rate is available.

In this work, we introduce a novel direct post-processing approach for calculating liquid water content: a bin-wise calculation of liquid water content, aggregated across all droplet size and velocity bins for each rain event. We use this bin-wise post-processing method as a benchmark against traditional representative droplet methods. We assume that the bin-wise approach, which incorporates all droplet bins in the droplet size distribution (DSD) for the calculation, offers the most accurate estimation. The main objective of this research is to assess how these different post-processing methods of rain data influence the modeled progression of damage. Additionally, we aim to determine which of the established methods aligns most closely with the new bin-wise approach and which ones introduc the most significant bias when compared to damages estimates based on bin-wise liquid water content.

2. Methodology

The damage progression in this study is based on the impingement model described in Bech et al [9]. The damage modeling workflow can be seen in Figure 1, showing how the input data are converted into blade erosion damage increments. In our study we use input data with a 10-minute time step, but the same modeling framework is adaptable to other time steps, e.g. hourly.

Figure 1. Visualization of the damage modelling, where input data is shown in green, modelled parameters in blue and liquid water content highlighted in orange.

The liquid water content (W_L) in a unit volume of air is calculated from the measured rain rate (R_m) and the average height (h) that the droplets have fallen during the time interval (Δt),

$$W_L = \frac{R_m \Delta t}{h} = \frac{R_m \Delta t}{V_f \Delta t} = \frac{R_m}{V_f} \quad (1)$$

where V_f is the average droplet fall velocity. When disdrometer data are not available, V_f is typically calculated with theory from the literature, such as described by Best [9]. Wind speed (U) is converted to blade tip speed of a chosen wind turbine, which in this study is the IEA 15

MW reference turbine [10]. The liquid water content is combined with the tip speed (V_{tip}) to estimate the impinging water at the blade tip (H_{tip}) for each time step,

$$H_{tip} = W_L V_{tip} \Delta t \quad (2)$$

We combine the impact speed of blade and droplets with a Wöhler curve, which, for the current model, is a VH curve (H for impingement and V for impact velocity). The VH curve gives a relation of droplet impact speed (V_{imp}) and the impinging rain at coating failure, or water column (H_{dam} measured in meters)

$$H_{dam} = H_0 \left(\frac{V_{imp}}{V_0} \right)^{-m} \quad (3)$$

where $V_{imp} = \sqrt{V_{tip}^2 + U^2}$, $V_0 = 1$ m/s is a normalization velocity, $H_0 = 2.85 \times 10^{22}$ m and $m = 10.5$ are fitting parameters found from least-squares fitting. In this study the chosen VH curve is described in Bech et al.[9] estimated with a spray mode in an indoor laboratory called a rain erosion tester and using specimen with typical modern coating material. For each time step of the observational data, we calculate a damage increment, which is the ratio of estimated blade rain rate (H_{tip}) over H_{dam} . The accumulated damage is expressed by the sum of the damage increments

$$D = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{H_{dam,i}}{H_{tip,i}} \quad (4)$$

where k is the number of time steps.

3. Data analysis

A time-series of disdrometer (Parsivel2, OTT) measurements observed during July 2019 to January 2022 and concurrent wind speed from the 125m tall meteorological mast at Risø test site. The disdrometer measures the DSD and the vertical fall velocities for all the droplets during rain events. These recordings were used to provide the model input for V_f and R_{meas} . Wind speeds were extrapolated from cup anemometer observations at 118 m and 125 m with an estimated average shear exponent to 150 m, which is the hub height of the IEA 15 MW wind turbine. All observational data were post-processed to a 10-minute time resolution. The disdrometer data was accessed in a database where the DSD, fall velocities (V_f), and rainfall intensities are stored every minute.

Typically, W_L is determined using the rain rate and fall velocity of a single representative droplet diameter for each rain event using Equation (1). Here we calculated the W_L using 4 different common approaches:

- (i) V_f corresponding to the mass-weighted mean droplet diameter of all measured droplets
- (ii) V_f is taken as the mean observed fall velocity of the diameter bin corresponding to the median volume of all measured droplets
- (iii) V_f corresponds to the arithmetic mean diameter of all measured droplets
- (iv) V_f is estimated from the rain rate only, based on the work of Best [8] relating R_{meas} to the droplet median diameter and corresponding terminal velocity

Further, we also calculate the liquid water content by summing the water volume for each droplet diameter and fall velocity bin, as provided by the disdrometer output, to calculate the total liquid water content of each rain event. In this bin-wise approach we avoid the need for assuming one representative droplet diameter for each event and the corresponding V_f . We use this direct estimation method of W_L , which considers the entire Droplet Size Distribution

(DSD), as a benchmark against W_L estimates based on approaches (i)-(iv). Note that the droplet median and fall velocity estimated with Best theory (iv) is a function of rain rate only. This theory is commonly used when rain rate is the only available measurement. The fall velocity is approximated by a polynomial function of third degree that describes terminal velocity of droplets

$$V_{term} = 0.0481d_d^3 - 0.8037d_d^2 + 4.621d_d \quad (5)$$

where d_d is the droplet diameter and V_{term} is the terminal velocity of droplets.

4. Results

Figure 2. Droplet fall velocity versus droplet diameter. The diameter is estimated with a mass-weighted mean (blue dots), median bin (orange dots), arithmetic mean (green dots), and estimated median with Best theory (red dots).

We investigate the droplet fall velocity as described and used in approaches (i)-(iv) in Section 3. For each 10-minute rain event we show the fall velocity as function of the representative droplet diameter in Figure 2. The droplet diameter is not used further for the damage calculations, but shown here for demonstrative purposes. The larger drops generally have a higher fall velocity and follow approximately the polynomial function in Equation 5. However, the measured droplets all have a lower fall velocity and a much higher spread compared to the theoretical terminal velocity of Best.

The droplet diameters that are estimated with the arithmetic mean (green dots) clearly have the smallest diameters among the estimates, while the mass-weighted mean and the diameter corresponding to the median volume of the measured diameters show the largest diameters. It can be seen how the droplet diameter bins are defined for the distrometer, as the median diameter estimates fall within these bins.

Figure 3 shows the liquid water content based on Equation 1 as function of rain rate for each rain event of the data set. The fall velocities that are based on approaches (i)-(iv) are shown in panels a)-d) respectively and each one is compared with the bin-wise approach, where the liquid water content is calculated for each droplet bin in the DSD and summed up to one value for each rain event. This method gives a more precise estimate of the total liquid water

Figure 3. The liquid water content shown as function of rain rate for each 10-minute rain event. The grey dots show the estimation where the liquid water content is determined for each droplet diameter bin and then summed. The colored marks correspond to colors in Figure 2.

content in the air, as we do not have to assume one representative fall velocity of the event. We see in panel a) good overlap between the bin-wise sum of W_L values and the ones estimated from the fall velocities corresponding to the mass-weighted mean droplet diameter, though the mass-weighted mean estimates are slightly lower for high rain rates. In panel b) we notice a good overlap between the estimated liquid water content in the whole rain rate range, but we note that there are both slight under- and over estimations for individual events. In panel c) the liquid water content is estimated with fall velocities corresponding to the arithmetic mean diameter. Here we note a clear overestimation of the W_L for all measured rain rates. Conversely, the liquid water content estimated with the Best theory is underestimated in the whole rain rate range.

Figure 4 shows the simulated cumulative sum of the damage increments, where erosion damage occurs when the damage increments add up to a value of one. We see that the highest estimated damages are associated with the approach (iii), the droplet mean method. This method gave, on average, the smallest droplets values among the estimation approaches. The smaller droplets result in lower V_f , leading to higher estimates of liquid water content in the air (as described in Equation 1).

On the contrary, we see that the lowest erosion damage predictions are from the median estimation method using the Best theory. This can be explained by the fact that V_f is estimated using a theoretical expression of droplet terminal velocity, resulting in higher average fall velocity values. Note that the wind speed and rainfall intensities are the same for all the damage progression curves. Therefore, the differences in damage estimates are a direct result of the

Figure 4. Cumulative sum of the modelled damage increments as function of time. The increment sum increases for each 10-minute rain event.

differences in liquid water estimation methods.

Table 1. The accumulated damage and relative bias for the different approaches of liquid water content estimations.

W_L approach	Accumulated damage	Relative bias
Mass-weighted mean (i)	0.108	-6%
Median volume bin (ii)	0.113	-2%
Arithmetic mean (iii)	0.153	22%
Median from Best (iv)	0.094	-19%

The accumulated damage predictions and relative biases are listed in Table 1. Here the bin-wise sum estimation approach is used as a reference to calculate the relative bias. We see that the the median bin approach gives the lowest bias of negative 2%, while the arithmetic mean approach leads to the highest bias of 22% and the Best method results in a 19% negative bias.

5. Discussion

The observed fall velocities of measured droplets are clearly lower than the Best theoretical terminal velocities (see Figure 2), a phenomenon attributed to potential coalescence or breakup of droplets in the atmosphere [11]. It should be noted that the measured droplet fall velocities are not necessarily equal to terminal velocities. Consequently, an updated theoretical approach for raindrop fall velocity should be considered, particularly for sites equipped with only rain gauges. This is of particular interest in the context of rain erosion studies and research.

When estimating a representative droplet diameter for calculating liquid water content, the arithmetic mean method proves unsuitable, as the liquid water content is clearly overestimated for these relatively small droplet diameters. This inadequacy is likely due to the fact that the droplets follow a positively skewed distribution, like the Weibull [8], the log-normal, or the exponential distribution [11]. The mean may not be in the middle of the distribution and therefore the median is often a better measure of central tendency for these distributions.

Among the post-processing approaches for liquid water estimation, both the mass-weighted mean method and the median volume droplet bin are the two approaches that come closest to the bin-wise sum of liquid water. However, the mass-weighted mean method slightly underpredicts W_L at high rain rates, potentially due to an overemphasis on the largest droplet diameters. Therefore, we recommend the use of the median volume droplet diameter, especially when a bin-wise sum is not a feasible option. This approach provides a more accurate representation of the total liquid water content, considering the distribution of droplet sizes in rain events.

In our study, we find that for a given amount of rainfall, large droplets will lead to less damage than small droplets. This can be explained by the lower fall velocity of smaller droplets, causing them to linger in the air for a longer duration. Consequently, the wind turbine blade, with its high tip speed, encounters a greater volume of impinging water from these smaller droplets. This is in some sense rather counterintuitive and in contrast with soil erosion research [12], where it is the raindrop kinetic energy that is considered a crucial factor for raindrop impact, which is governed by the fall velocity of large droplets. For modern wind turbines, operating at rated wind speed, the governing velocity of the damage model is the tip speed of the blade, not the fall velocity of the droplet, as it is an order of magnitude smaller than the tip velocity.

Several damage modeling frameworks, e.g. [2, 13], are founded on the Springer model [14]. Unlike the current model, which is based on the accumulated impingement, the Springer model is based on specific droplet impacts, where the number of rain droplets per unit volume of rainfall is calculated. The relation between specific droplet impacts and impingement is: $3/(2d)$, where d is the droplet diameter [9], giving a straight forward conversion between the two. Very similar to the liquid water content. It is therefore a similarly crucial for these damage models to calculate the amount of water content in the air accurately. Discrepancies in these computations within Springer-based models could yield comparable biases to those reported in this study.

The rain measurements analyzed in this study are limited to a single site at Risø campus. In future research, we plan to extend our analysis to incorporate measurements from additional sites, as different climates may result in varying DSD, potentially influencing the findings.

6. Conclusions

In this study, we have evaluated four different post-processing methods of distrometer data for estimating the liquid water content in the air and bench-marked those against a more sophisticated post-processing of the raw data in which the liquid water content is determined experimentally. Using these W_L estimates for accumulated damage prediction, the median volume method showed the lowest bias of -2%, compared to the bin-wise summation. However, the arithmetic mean method resulted in the largest positive bias of 22%, while the theoretical median derived from Best's approach resulted in the largest negative bias of -19%.

The theoretical and measured fall velocities of droplets were compared, revealing discrepancies that underscore the need for an updated theoretical approach to raindrop fall velocity, especially for sites equipped solely with rain gauges.

The estimations of liquid water content directly impact the predictions of the modeled damage, with an overestimation in liquid water content resulting in overestimations of the cumulative damage increments and vice versa.

Our study has highlighted the significant impact of different liquid water content estimation methods on erosion damage predictions. It is important to note that these variations in damage estimates were attributed solely to the different liquid water content estimation approaches, as the wind speed and rainfall intensities were the same for all damage progression curves.

Our findings reveal that, for a given amount of rainfall, smaller droplets induce more damage than larger droplets. This counterintuitive observation is only relevant for modern wind turbines operating at rated wind speeds, where the tip velocity of the blade, rather than the fall velocity of the droplet, governs the damage prediction.

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